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GASTRONOMY AND CUISINE ART

Xashimova Shaxnoza Shuxrat kizi

Tashkent State University of Economics PhD researcher of the
“Hotel Business Management” department

ORCID: 0009-0008-2971-5129

Abstract: Cuisine, a significant source of income for the tourism industry and a key attraction for tourist destinations, plays a crucial role in representing national cultures. Today, culinary professionals have become indispensable to the tourism sector. This study examines the attitudes of gastronomy and culinary arts students toward the cuisine department, where they will be employed after graduation. A survey technique was used to collect data, which was then analyzed statistically.

The results indicate that gastronomy and culinary arts students hold positive attitudes toward the cuisine department. Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) was conducted to assess the structural validity of the findings, confirming that the proposed model is appropriate. Additionally, a positive and significant correlation was found between the overall scale and its subdimensions. The research further revealed that environmental factors are the most influential dimension in shaping attitudes toward the cuisine department.

Key words: Kitchen, education, attitude, gastronomy, tourism.

INTRODUCTION

Food is not merely a biological necessity or a functional product; it is also a cultural object that extends beyond its nutritional value. It is consumed for its symbolic and aesthetic significance, as well as for the emotions it evokes. As an expression of social connection, food encompasses sharing meals and dining together, which defines fundamental social relationships.¹

Today, people eat not only to satisfy their hunger but also to experience new flavors. In pursuit of diverse culinary experiences, individuals dine outside their homes and even travel to different cities and countries to taste unique and delicious foods. Consequently, the role of food in people's lives is increasing day by day. Food consumption has become an integral component of tourism, evolving beyond a mere necessity into a touristic recreational activity. In the hospitality industry, no matter how modern, advanced, or luxurious a hotel's kitchen may be—regardless of the quality of materials and raw ingredients used in food preparation the most crucial element in the kitchen is the workforce. The success or failure of a hotel's kitchen is primarily determined by its personnel. Achieving culinary excellence depends on the selection of skilled professionals, making it essential for kitchens to employ a sufficient number of qualified and well-trained staff.

In this context, tourism education programs should emphasize practical training over theoretical instruction, particularly in food and beverage management and culinary arts. The quality of food produced in a kitchen plays a significant role in shaping tourist satisfaction, whether they are staying at a hotel or dining at an independent food and beverage establishment. Therefore, tourism businesses must prioritize hiring a highly qualified workforce when selecting kitchen staff.

¹ Bessiere, J. (1998). Local development and heritage: Traditional food and cuisine as tourist attractions in rural areas. *Sociologia Ruralis*. 38, 21-34

In our country, formally and informally educated culinary professionals are trained to meet the needs of the tourism industry. The primary goal of culinary education is to produce well-equipped professionals for the hospitality sector. In Turkey, undergraduate programs such as “Gastronomy,” “Gastronomy and Culinary Arts,” and “Culinary Arts and Management” serve as key sources of employment for the food, beverage, and tourism industries. Additionally, associate degree programs in “Cooking” provide vocational training in culinary arts.² This study aims to analyze the attitudes of undergraduate students studying gastronomy and culinary arts toward the kitchen department.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The word “*kitchen*”, which means “*a place where food is cooked*” in Arabic, has been adopted into Turkish from the Arabic word “*matbah*”. The concept of a kitchen refers to both a cultural phenomenon and a physical space. The culinary traditions of nations related to nutrition are referred to as *kitchens*. A kitchen is a cultural entity that encompasses the tools and equipment used in the preparation of food and beverages, the techniques of culinary arts, and dining ceremonies.

When considered as a physical space, a kitchen is defined as the place where all types of food are prepared, cooked, and consumed. It is also the area where food production is carried out in the targeted quantity, quality, and standards in food and beverage businesses. The kitchen is regarded as the *heart* of the food and beverage industry. It is also one of the most important branches of the tourism sector. In touristic activities, individuals spend the most on food and beverages after accommodation.

It is stated that gastronomy, which has gained prominence in recent years, has evolved into a scientific field that studies the elements that shape kitchen and culinary culture. The word gastronomy, frequently used in daily life by food enthusiasts, professionals in the food and beverage sector, and the media, is a relatively new term that has been borrowed from French into Turkish. According to the Turkish Language Association, the word gastronomy has two definitions: “the passion for eating good food” and “a well-organized, healthy, enjoyable, and delicious cuisine, meal order, and system.” In its simplest definition, gastronomy is described as “the science and art of eating good food.”

Today, gastronomy has evolved beyond being merely a cultural practice within societies; it has become a crucial aspect of marketing and promoting a country, making it an inseparable part of the tourism experience. Success in the tourism industry is closely linked to culinary services. Food and beverage services, which form the foundation of the hospitality sector, are also a primary source of revenue. Regardless of location, people seek places that offer comfort, friendly service, and delicious food and beverages.³

Moreover, individuals have the fundamental right to access and consume services that provide reliable, affordable, high-quality, and well-balanced nutrition while promoting healthy eating habits.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study aims to examine the attitudes of future kitchen professionals, who play a crucial role in the tourism industry, towards their work environment. Specifically, it seeks to assess the perceptions of gastronomy and culinary arts students regarding the kitchen department, identify the key sub-dimensions influencing these attitudes, determine the most impactful factor, and explore whether students’ demographic characteristics significantly affect their attitudes.

The fundamental assumption of this research is that various factors influence the attitudes of gastronomy and culinary arts students towards the kitchen department.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The universe of the study consists of students of the Gastronomy and Culinary Arts Department of Balıkesir University. There are 1st, 2nd, 3rd year students in the Gastronomy and Culinary Arts Department of Balıkesir University, Faculty of Tourism. Accordingly, the current number of students was determined by examining the 2014–2016 ÖSYS Higher Education Programs and Quota Guides, and the student numbers were confirmed by consulting with the faculty’s student affairs office. It was determined that there were 80 students in total: 30 in the 1st year, 25 in the 2nd year, and 25 in the 3rd year in the Gastronomy and Culinary Arts Department of Balıkesir University, Faculty of Tourism.

2 Çakır, M. (2010). Otel işletmelerinin mutfak bölümünde istihdam edilen personelin eğitim sürecinin değerlendirilmesi: İstanbul’daki 5 yıldızlı zincir otellere yönelik bir alan çalışması. (Yayınlanmamış Yüksek Lisans Tezi), İstanbul Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü, İstanbul.

3 Güldemir, O. (2015). Yiyecek içecek bölümü mutfak planlaması. Turizm İşletmelerinde Yiyecek-içecek Yönetimi (Ed. Murat Doğdubay). Ankara: Garfiker Yayınları.

Since it was possible to reach the entire sample in the study, the complete count method was used, and the prepared questionnaire was applied to 79 students who were actively studying in the Gastronomy and Culinary Arts Department of Balıkesir University, Faculty of Tourism, through face-to-face interviews.⁴

Table 1. The hypotheses of the research⁵.

H1= There is a significant relationship between the demographic characteristics of the students and their attitudes towards the kitchen department.
H2= There is a significant relationship between the importance of the kitchen department (IMD) dimension and their attitudes towards the general kitchen department.
H3= There is a significant relationship between the job qualifications (JQ) dimension and their attitudes towards the general kitchen department.
H4= There is a significant relationship between the environmental impact (EI) dimension and their attitudes towards the general kitchen department.
H5= There is a significant relationship between the Talents (YE) dimension and their attitudes towards the general kitchen department.
H6= There is a significant relationship between the Turkish cuisine (TM) dimension and their attitudes towards the general kitchen department.

The research survey consists of two parts. The first part includes questions aimed at determining the socio-demographic characteristics of gastronomy and culinary arts students participating in the study. The second part utilizes the Attitudes Towards the Kitchen Department (AAT) scale, developed by Tekin and Çiğdem in 2015. This scale comprises 28 statements, five dimensions, and follows a five-point Likert scale to assess students' attitudes toward the kitchen department. The primary reason for selecting this scale is its recent development, established validity and reliability, and clear language.

To test the structural validity of the survey form used in the research, it was administered to students in the gastronomy and culinary arts department at the Faculty of Tourism, Balıkesir University, during the first week of November 2016. The surveys were conducted through one-on-one interviews with students. A total of 80 surveys were printed, and an attempt was made to reach all students. Ultimately, 79 students participated, and the collected data were used in the research analysis. The study included frequency analyses of socio-demographic characteristics, as well as calculations of arithmetic mean, standard deviation, correlation analysis, independent sample t-tests, one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA), reliability analyses, simple linear regression analysis, and confirmatory factor analysis. The statistical analyses were conducted using SPSS 21.0 and LISREL 8.80 software.

Table 2. The socio-demographic characteristics of gastronomy and culinary arts students.⁶

Male	53.2%
Female	46.8%
18-20 years old students	62%
24 years old and above	5.1%

This section presents the analyses, findings, and interpretations of the research, which aims to determine the socio-demographic characteristics of gastronomy and culinary arts students, their attitudes toward the kitchen department, the factors influencing these attitudes, and the validation of the attitude scale for the kitchen department. Among the students who participated in the study, 53.2% were male, and 46.8% were female. In terms of age distribution, 62% were between 18 and 20 years old, 32.9% were between 21 and 23 years old, and 5.1% were 24 years old or older.

The aim of this study was to test the Attitude Scale Towards the Kitchen Department, developed by Tekin and Çiğdem, which consists of 28 items across 5 dimensions, on gastronomy and culinary arts students. Additionally, the study aimed to measure students' attitudes toward the kitchen department, identify the sub-dimensions affecting the MDYT scale, and determine which dimension has the most significant impact. To analyze the relationship between students' attitudes toward the kitchen department and their socio-

4 Koçak, N. (2012). *Yiyecek İçecek Hizmetleri Yönetimi*. Ankara: Detay Yayıncılık.

5 Kınalı, N. (2014). Destinasyonun turistik çekim gücü içerisinde bölge mutfağının önemi ve Erzurum mutfağı örneği. (Yayınlanmamış Yüksek Lisans Tezi), Atatürk Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü, Erzurum

6 Sevim, B. ve Görkem, O. (2015). Gastronomi ve aşçılık programlarında gıda güvenliği donanım altyapısının değerlendirilmesi. *Uluslararası Alanya İşletme Fakültesi Dergisi*. 7 (1), 59-67.

demographic characteristics, t-tests and one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) were conducted. These tests examined differences in attitudes based on general scale measurements and sub-dimensions. Among the tested hypotheses, H1 was partially accepted.

Furthermore, simple linear regression analysis was performed to identify the dimensions influencing the Attitude Scale Towards the Kitchen Department and to determine the extent to which the sub-dimensions explain the overall scale. The results indicated that H2, H3, H4, H5, and H6 hypotheses were accepted. Correlation and regression analyses revealed a strong positive relationship between the MDYT scale and its sub-dimensions. The study concluded that the scale, originally developed by Tekin and Çiğdem, was designed with a positive perspective. Among the sub-dimensions, "environmental impact" was identified as the most influential factor affecting the MDYT scale. The findings suggest that the growing perception of cooking as a more popular and respected profession in the future significantly contributes to this outcome. Additionally, it is believed that family and close social circles play a crucial role in shaping attitudes toward the kitchen department, further reinforcing the study's results.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The kitchen department plays a crucial role in hotel businesses. The quality of work performed in the kitchen is exceptionally high, and environmental factors positively influence working conditions in this department. Additionally, individual abilities play a significant role in determining suitability for kitchen-related tasks, particularly in relation to Turkish cuisine.

It has been concluded that interest in Turkish cuisine is a key factor in the selection of the culinary department. The work carried out in the kitchen is perceived as engaging, enjoyable, and highly satisfying, offering better opportunities for long-term employment and professional experience compared to other departments.

Furthermore, it has been determined that the kitchen department is essential in promoting the country, establishing a brand image, enhancing customer satisfaction, fostering business competition, generating high revenue, encouraging guests to revisit the same hotels, and facilitating cultural exchange. Employees in this field recognize that they possess the artistic skills, talents, and teamwork abilities necessary for success in the kitchen department.

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